

City as an Ecological landscape: redefining urban ecology of a multi-layered city Karachi–case study of Lyari expressway

Mahwish Ghulam Rasool

Mahwishgr04@gmail.com

Mahwish.rasool@indusvalley.edu.pk

Indus Valley School of Art and Architecture Karachi, Pakistan

Department of Interior Design

Abstract

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Architects are creators of the built environment, enabling them to imagine, design, and plan it and to impact the lives of many. This practice bears greater responsibility for improving people's lives and well-being and advances sustainable design approaches. This raises a deeper concept of urban eco-planning in architecture and urban planning, which designers should understand and recognise as essential to their effectiveness as creators of the built environment.

This Paper aims to establish the concept of urban ecology, its importance, and its relevance within the paradigm of urban design. Furthermore, the objective is to establish the need for an urban ecosystem and to examine how the built environment is shaped by it, while investigating the phenomena of cultural landscape and ecology as part of the city image.

Secondly, to investigate the impacts of the Lyari Expressway on the city's physical and ecological character, the Paper will shift from 'infrastructure-centred' comprehensive planning to 'people-centred strategic planning'. Karachi city will be the focus of the Study.

The paper is structured in three parts. The first section reviews the literature on the importance of eco-planning and urban ecology in sustainable urban development. This section addresses the major environmental problems arising from urban development, existing policy frameworks for addressing these problems, and the necessity and benefits of using eco-planning as a tool in the urban development process. The second section presents a brief introduction to the context and a selected case study of LEW, its conceptions and impacts on urban ecological landscapes. The third part will present a comparative analysis using an international case study and summarise the findings of the earlier sections.

Introduction

In recent years, cities have experienced incremental infrastructure growth, accompanied by alarming signs of environmental problems stemming from the negative impacts of various urban activities. Degradation of natural resources, climate change, and development pressures pose threats to urban ecology. It is estimated that more than 50% of the world's population now lives in cities and urban areas, creating immense challenges for designers seeking to plan environmentally conscious cities that mitigate the impacts of such developments. (World Fact Book-2016)

In response to these environmental impacts, urban planning policies have shifted from a traditional infrastructure approach to a people-centric development model, with ecology, culture, politics, and economics as the main indicators of sustainable practices. Cities have begun developing new strategies to improve the quality of urban ecosystems. An important function of urban ecological planning is to provide healthy and sustainable environments for both natural systems and communities. The term "Eco city" was first coined in 1987 by Richard Register, who used it to refer to a sustainable city for the future. ¹

Therefore, **Eco-planning** is a functional requirement for cities to establish a sustainable built environment. In eco-planning, natural resources are used most effectively; it protects human and environmental health, reduces environmental pollution, and provides green corridors. As cited by Williams (2000, p.11), **eco-planning** refers to "strategies and techniques that combine urbanism and nature to create healthy, civilising, and enriching places to live". It means "a living area governed more by nature than legislature; and a sustainable human settlement based on ecological balance, community self-reliance, and participatory democracy". Eco-planning is a fundamentally multidimensional concept that provides a wide range of environmental, economic, and social benefits to local governments, developers, and the community as a whole. Environmentally, it creates ecologically effective green areas, reduces ecological risks, and improves the quality of water, air and soil. Economically, it prevents urban sprawl and traffic congestion and provides better utilisation of existing Infrastructure. Socially, it reduces health risks and improves the quality of urban life and city Services (e.g., health, education, transportation, recreation) (Galifianakis, 2006).²

Figure 1. East River waterfront project and Gowanus Canal project.

Urban ecology is an interdisciplinary field that integrates the natural and social sciences, which is imperative for a holistic approach to incorporating ecology into urban planning. **Urban ecology** studies the relationships between humans and their surroundings, including cities and urbanising landscapes. This recent, interdisciplinary field seeks to understand the coexistence of human and ecological processes in urban environments and to help humans build more sustainable ways of living. It is a subfield of ecology and has strong connections with disciplines such as sociology, geography, urban planning, landscape architecture, engineering, economics, anthropology, climatology, and public health. Therefore, urban ecology is the study of humans in urban environments, of nature in cities, and of the relationships between humans and nature. The term also addressed questions about the effects of urbanisation on the ecology of living organisms, as well as the differences between ecological processes in cities and those in other environments.³

There is mutual interaction between cities and ecological processes, whereby both affect one another. This is true not only within the boundaries of the cities but also beyond them. As a result of this strong interaction, it is neither possible nor useful to insulate human and natural components of urban ecological studies. Similarly, the study of urban ecology is vital for understanding where and how human activity harms the urban environment and how to improve human living conditions without causing further environmental damage.

Figure 2. Urban ecology chart.⁴

Introduction to context

Karachi is the largest city in Pakistan and the 7th-largest city in the world. Located along the Arabian Sea shoreline, Karachi has experienced phenomenal urban growth over the years, characteristic of a major port city in the developing world. Established as a small local port and subsequently developed into a military base by the British in 1839. City growth gained importance after the British consolidated their activities in Sindh and Punjab and used Karachi as a major transit hub for goods and military purposes. The city's physical infrastructure development continued haphazardly. The 1861 establishment of railway connections between the upcountry provinces marked a breakthrough in the development of tanneries, oil storage, wood-processing industries, and warehousing. These activities attracted labour from adjoining provinces, leading to the migration and settlement of inhabitants along the banks of the Lyari River. **By 1900**, the city's population had exceeded 100,000.⁵

This process continued until 1947, and the city grew steadily, supported by stable trade and commerce. The port/shipping facilities for transportation of raw materials and finished products also expanded. Karachi Airport was one of the earliest airports in the subcontinent, linking the city to remote regions. Moreover, the city had a responsive population that remained keenly interested in these developments. In 1946, the city had a population of 435,000 and was labelled as one of the best-maintained cities of South Asia (Ahmed, 1998).

Following independence from colonial rule, economic growth continued to accelerate amid the influx of refugees from India. The population increased by 2.5-fold over four years, reaching 1,050,000 in 1951. Since then, the city's anomalous growth has accelerated, and it now has a population of over 15 million, with a 4.5 per cent annual growth rate.⁶

Karachi remained the hub of economic activity in Pakistan and a major magnet for employment. It accounts for 50 per cent of the country's bank deposits, and 72 per cent of all issued capital is from Karachi (Hasan, 2002; Ahmed, 1998). According to recent surveys, the city had an estimated population of over 23.5 million in 2013. Karachi was the 7th-largest city in the world by Jan 2016 and the 11th-largest urban agglomeration in the world.

Figure 3. Lyari settlement map.

This enormous population and the lack of effective environmental planning have generated various **ecological** problems. Biodiversity in Karachi has not been studied previously because most policymakers considered it of little importance. There has been a substantial reduction in the city's green spaces over the past 25 years, accompanied by a concomitant increase in urban development. Beyond its urban landscapes, the city faces numerous environmental challenges due to inadequate ecological planning.

Karachi ecology

Karachi is situated 130 km west of the Indus estuary and on the northern coast of the Arabian Sea, which gives a marine influence to its climate. Undoubtedly, it has one of the most favourable geostrategic locations, close to three continents: Europe, Africa, and Asia. Numerous artificial and built features, including the Arabian Sea coast, urban mangrove clusters, and diverse urban natural assets, characterise Karachi. One study by *Salman Qureshi*^{1, 2} and *Jürgen H. Breuste* found that Karachi has more than 1,200 natural spaces, comprising formal green areas and urban nature types. Karachi has numerous natural water channels that contribute to the city's ecology and serve as flood-control mechanisms. The two most important river channels are the Malir River in the northeast and the Lyari River in the east.⁷

Lyari River has an important ecological location in the Karachi city it is originated from the north (Hills of Kirthar) extended till the mangrove forest the channel flows down into the Sandpit backwaters of the Arabian Sea, it is a small ephemeral fresh water stream considered as one of the major corridors of development since its conception the first settlement is believed to have been formed in 1729. The **LEW** project was conceptualised to reduce the volume of heavy traffic passing through the port to the superhighway heading upcountry, as an alternative to the development of a northern bypass proposed in the Karachi master plan of 1975-1985.⁸

In 1986, a group of public-spirited citizens proposed the construction of the Lyari Expressway. This proposal consisted of a plan to build a road from the port, along the Lyari River to the superhighway, which is one of Karachi's main links with the rest of Pakistan. It was proposed as a 16.5 km, 8-lane expressway with four lanes on each side, comprising two interchanges, five overpasses, and five underpasses. Moreover, two lanes will be constructed on each bank of the Lyari River.

A government study found that constructing the Lyari expressway along the riverbanks was infeasible because more than 100,000 people living along the river at the time would have had to be evicted. However, the idea of the expressway appealed to politicians and Planners, and in 1989, the Karachi Development Authority engaged the Canadian International Development Agency (CIDA) on the Lyari Expressway project. CIDA proposed an elevated corridor on columns in the middle of the river as the most feasible option, as it would not displace any Lyari corridor communities. The cost of the elevated expressway was estimated at 6 billion rupees. However, in 1993, heavy rainfall inundated the lower-lying settlements of the Lyari corridor; as a result, planners proposed constructing the Lyari expressway along both banks to provide flood protection. (Hasan, 2005).

The Urban Resource Centre (URC), a Karachi-based NGO engaged in research and advocacy, objected to both proposals. The URC objected that the expressway was not an alternative to the northern bypass. It would cause immense noise and air pollution in the most densely populated areas of Karachi's settlements; the elevated option would be aesthetically unsightly; and the riverbank roads would displace poor communities. Nor would the expressway project open land for the relocation of inner-city markets, warehousing, and informal manufacturing units, as the northern bypass would. Advocacy and mobilisation of affected and concerned communities began soon. The Lyari Nadi Welfare Association (LNWA) was formed, comprising 42 communities. Meanwhile, URC also developed various alternative plans. As a result, the project was delayed. The Canadian government withdrew its support for the project. The project was further modified after the involvement of the Frontier Works Organisation (FWO) – A military contracting enterprise – and, as a result, the underpasses were abandoned in favour of bridges over the existing bridges, and the cost increased to 3,200 million rupees. (Hasan, 2005; Ahmed, 2003 and 2004).

The changes to the project set increase the number of affected and also raise the estimated cost of LEW. Following the 1996 public hearing and the extensive demolitions, it was decided to construct the northern bypass and abandon the LEW. Subsequently, in 2001, the Karachi Port

Trust, after considerable consultation with interest groups, finalised the proposal for building the northern bypass. It was to join the super-highway well beyond Karachi's municipal limits to minimise congestion on Karachi's main exit point to the northeast. However, in June 2001, the government decided to build both the northern bypass and the Lyari expressway within the northern bypass budget, based on the FWO plan and in violation of the decisions arising from the **1996** public hearings. (Hasan 2005)

The Government of Pakistan is a signatory to the Global Plan of Action of the UN City Summit (Habitat II) of 1996, which is against forced evictions and demolitions. Section 12 of the Pakistan Environmental Act 1997 requires any proponent of a project to submit an environmental impact assessment if the project is likely to cause any adverse environmental effect and, on this basis, must seek approval (or modification) of the plan from the relevant federal authority. Lyari Expressway has not done this. (Hasan 2005)

Issues related to LEW

It is estimated that the entire expressway section will be completed by June 2017. If used for heavy port-related traffic, it will cause severe environmental pollution and further degradation along the already heavily polluted Lyari corridor.

The construction of the LEW exacerbated the existing environmental problems of congestion, pollution, and heritage degradation in the areas adjacent to it. **The areas adjacent to Lyari comprise city quarters where the city's decaying architectural heritage and old communities are located. The degradation of these areas is attributable to the presence of wholesale markets, storage, warehousing, and transport terminals that serve port activity and dock labour.** The residents of these areas and the businessmen in the existing markets have been demanding the removal and relocation of the markets due to congestion and unsanitary conditions they have caused in the inner city, which are degrading the architectural heritage, harming residents' health, and hindering mobility.

Figure 4. LEW route map.

The apparent rationale for constructing the Lyari Expressway was to address these problems. However, in the absence of a land use plan as a part of the design of the Expressway, it is likely to result in greater congestion when the poorly thought-through

The project has been implemented and is operational. The solid waste and recycling industry along the Lyari Riverbed is also likely to be affected by the project. Despite Karachi remaining the country's principal economic, financial, and business hub, the development process has been ad hoc. Several plans for the development of transport infrastructure have been prepared; however, no one has been granted the requisite legal and administrative cover. Among the various plans prepared for the city, the Karachi Development Plans (1973-85) and (1986-2000) were the most comprehensive in terms of concept, approach, and applications within the planning process.⁹

Visionaries and planners anticipated numerous proposals for the LEW corridor upgrade, including development options to mitigate the impacts of LEW after its completion. One of the proposals considered the Lyari River estuarine wetland ecology as an integrated Ecosystem and aimed to develop strategies and guidelines for preserving wetland ecology through community participation

and the involvement of other relevant stakeholders, to reduce the impacts of the massive structure. Planner Farhan Anwar prepared this proposal. A similar approach has worked effectively in different cities; one case study Karachi should learn from is Seoul, and another comparative study is the revitalisation of the Los Angeles River.

Figure 5. Lyari River interchange map.

The figure 5 shows Lyari river channel on city level map which passes through four interchanges starting from Soharb Goth which is an entry point of Karachi and have open land for recreation development passing through civic center interchange one of the busiest location of the city where there are various amenity plots available with the river channel for urban recreation, moving to the garden interchange which have various listed heritage both in terms of building and landscapes and finally passes through Mariphur interchange to the Arabian sea with proximity of mangroves. The channel contains several suitable locations for city-level urban parks, which can provide breathing zones for citizens and help protect the ecological corridor.

CASE STUDY SEOUL RIVER DEVELOPMENT

Seoul is one of the fastest-growing cities in the world. The population of Seoul increased considerably between 1960 and 2002, and, in turn, the ownership of personal automobiles increased. Due to rapid urbanisation, the city mayor decided to construct an elevated highway along the river, 5.6 km in length. The project was completed in 1976 and is considered a successful example of South Korea's modernisation.¹⁰

By 2000, the Cheonggyecheon area was considered the most congested and noisy part of Seoul, in need of revitalisation. In July 2003, the then-mayor of Seoul initiated a project to remove the elevated highway and restore the stream. Despite this, the restoration of Cheonggyecheon was deemed important because it aligned with the movement to reintroduce nature to the city and to promote more eco-friendly urban design. Other goals of the project were to restore the region's history and culture, which had been lost for 30 years.¹¹

Figure 6. Cheonggyecheon River.

Between 2003 and 2005, an elevated highway that crossed Seoul's Cheonggyecheon River was demolished to improve the area's environmental and aesthetic conditions. Now a city highlight visited by 90,000 pedestrians daily, the restoration is a model for urban renewal projects worldwide. In the case of the infrastructure development of the Lyari expressway, the ecology of the river was

Completely ignored, the impacts of these monstrous constructions on the river's ecological landscape are enormous and adversely affect the city's urban ecology.¹²

Recommendations /proposals

Proposal 1

Lyari channel, as Lyari Park, and as a hybrid landscape

This proposal was prepared by the Ned University research cell in collaboration with the Asia Link program in a collaborative studio that addresses the Lyari River through a series of localised interventions that will respond to the specific, concrete places along the river where transformations are likely and impending. The project introduces the concept of river landscape and urban fabric by incorporating water purification plants, developing green open spaces along the river channel at multiple design scales, and connecting these open spaces to the heritage landscapes along the riverbed.¹³

Figure 7. Asia Link Collaborative Studio Proposal 2006.

Proposal 2

Lyari channel as an ecological corridor

This proposal was developed by the NED final-year students of 2009 in a comprehensive environmental design studio led by several research academics and planners. Many proposals aim to determine when LEW will be fully built and how it can still achieve a cohesive design solution that addresses various environmental problems while benefiting the broader population. The proposal I presented addresses the holistic integration of ecology and urban recreation through urban parks at two major interchanges of the Lyari corridor: Soharp Goth and the Maripur corridor, given their open-space accessibility and city location.

The proposal further discussed upgrading the Maripur exchange, revising the overall FARs, developing appropriate housing along the corridor, and implementing a city recreation intervention, including a mini-forest and a treated-water channel before it flows into the Arabian Sea. ¹⁴

Figure 8. Design proposal Maripur interchange CED 2009

CONCLUSION

“A city is not an accident but the result of coherent visions and aims.” — Leon Krier.

Thus, a successful city cannot operate efficiently in isolation from its environment. It must balance the social, economic and environmental needs. A successful city must offer investors security, infrastructure, and efficiency, and should also prioritise the needs of its citizens in all planning activities. Poor urban planning and management can have severe results for the urban economy, the environment and society.

In various ways, the built environment connects with both proximate and distant ecological processes. A sustainable design approach should include higher standards of environmental efficiency and performance, the use of clean energy, pollution control, solid waste management, and resource conservation. The ongoing research will further emphasise the shift from a more arbitrary approach to a radical ecological approach to future urban planning. Consequently, this concern will lead to the development of ecological priorities and to new frameworks for preventing ecological degradation in cities.

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